

COMPONENT FATTY ACIDS OF KĀHU (*LACTUCA SCARIOLA*, LINN) SEED OIL

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The seed oil of *Lactuca scariola*, Linn contains the following component fatty acids: caproic (2.1%), palmitic (1.8%), stearic (1.3%), arachidic (0.1%) oleic (36.5%) and linoleic (55.1%). It contains 0.6% of trilinolein and thus in spite of high percentage of linoleic acid there is an even distribution of fatty acids in the glycerides.

The seeds also contain a high percentage (3.1% on oil) of unseaponifiable matter. Arsenic in mere traces, iron, phosphorus, sodium, potassium, calcium, aluminium, nitrate, chloride have also been found in the seeds.

Lactuca scariola, Linn belongs to the N. O. *Compositæ*, and the plant is widely grown in Western Himalayas. It is known as lettuce in English and Kāhu or Kahoo in Hindustani. The plant is 1-3 ft. in height generally, but sometimes it is 6 ft. high. The seeds are oblong, about 1 cm. long and 1-2 mm. wide in the centre and resembles to some extent those of Caraway seeds. The seeds are used in India for relieving cough, asthma, pertussis and insomnia etc. The oil of the seeds is reputed to be beneficial for relieving melancholia, headache, inflammations and epilepsy and has hypnotic and antipyretic properties. The oil is also used as a cure for falling hair.

The seeds contain mere traces of arsenic and a fairly good amount of iron, phosphorus. On account of high content (35.5%) of oil of great medicinal value in the seeds which are available in plenty in India, the oil should form a good and cheap substitute for the more expensive almond oil. Seed is grown in crops and has not been commercially utilised so far.

The Kāhu oil is semi-drying in nature and has a high percentage of unsaturated acids: oleic (36.5%), linoleic (55.1%) saturated acids (5.3%), caproic (2.1%), palmitic (1.8%), stearic and (1.3%) arachidic (0.1%) and high percentage of unseaponifiable matter (3.1%). This conforms to the generalisation of Hilditch that the seed fats of *Compositas* family contain a fairly high percentage of unsaturated acids,

In spite of the high content of linoleic acid (55.1%) in the mixed fatty acids of the oil, trilinolein determined does not exceed 0.6% in the glycerides. Moreover, fully saturated glycerides are absent in the oil. This gives a support to the even distribution theory of Hilditch (Colli and Hilditch, *Biochem. J.*, 1929, 23, 1273) in seed oils namely (a) that in the seed-fats the component fatty acids are evenly distributed throughout the glyceride molecules, and (b) that fully saturated glycerides are produced in very small quantity in kernel fats, except when the amount of saturated fatty acids present is greater than that necessary to link with unsaturated fatty acids (in the form of mixed glycerides) in the molar ratio of about 1.3-1.4 of saturated to 1.0 of unsaturated fatty acids.

EXPERIMENTAL

The oil was obtained by cold pressing of the seeds in a small press and clarified by filtration. The oil is of a greenish yellow colour and possesses a pleasant smell and

somewhat sharp taste. It can be used for medicinal purposes and also for edible purposes after refining.

No data about the oil except a few characteristics of Egyptian oils are available and these along with those of the Indian oil are given in Table I.

TABLE I

General characteristics of Kahu oil.

Particulars.	<i>Lectuca scarola</i> (Indian).	<i>L. Scarola oleifera</i> (Egyptian).*
% oil in seeds	35.5	36.1
Specific gravity	—	0.9283
Refractive index	1.4879 at 25°	1.4682
Sap. Equiv.	290.6	293.0
Iodine value	123.5	127.6
Acid value	8.5	10.6
Unsaponifiable matter	3.0%	—

Composition of Fatty acids of Kahu Fat.—The oil (300 g.) was saponified with alcoholic potassium hydroxide and mixed acids, liberated, had saponification equivalent 280.5 and Iodine value 132.5. These acids were subjected to lead-salt separation in alcoholic solution and resolved into solid, liquid and acids, which were separately esterified to methyl esters. The esters were fractionally distilled under high vacuum of 1 mm. pressure. Each fraction was analysed and the acids in these were identified by suitable methods (Tables II and III).

TABLE II

Acids	%	Corresponding methyl esters Sapon. equiv.	Iodine value.
"Solid" (S)	3.33	282.9	3.7
"Liquid" (L)	96.67	285.0	132.8

TABLE III

(i) *Methyl esters of liquid (L) and Solid Acids (S).*

Liquid acid					Liquid acid				
No.	Wt.	B.p.	S.E.	I.V.	No.	Wt.	B.p.	S.E.	I.V.
L ₁	31.68 g.	154-170	274.3	130.5	L ₁ (a)	6.57 g.	165-179	269.9	128.0
L ₂	6.27	170-172	275.0	131.5	L ₁ (b)	8.20	176-180	274.2	130.6
L ₃	8.73	174-176	278.3	132.9	L ₁ (c)	8.54	179-184	276.9	131.9
L ₄	8.09	176-177	290.0	134.9	L ₁ (d)	1.50	Residue	277.0	134.5
L ₅	5.85	176-178	318.5	136.8	Solid acids				
L ₆	7.38	Residue	325.0	138.2	S ₁	2.58	169-161	272.0	3.51
"	Acids	ex N-S (Found)	319.1	141.9	S ₂	2.29	181-193	280.5	3.40
"	Esters	ex N-S (Calculated)	333.1	135.9	S ₃	2.01	Residue	301.2	4.20

* E. Griffiths—Jones. Rep. Pub. Health Laboratories, 1916, 1, and Bull. Imp. Inst., 1919, 37.

Identification of Acids.—The individual ester fractions mentioned below were hydrolysed by alcoholic potash and then potassium salts were oxidised with ice-cold potassium permanganate solution in dilute aqueous alkaline solution. Saturated fatty acids were separated from hydroxy fatty acids (produced by oxidation of ethylenic acids) by hot petroleum ether. The saturated acids were crystallised from alcohol and hydroxy acid from ethyl acetate and water.

L_1 (a):—Dihydroxystearic acid of m.p. 129° and tetrahydroxystearic acid of m.p. 169° were identified, showing the presence of $\Delta^9:10$ oleic acid and $\Delta^9:10,12:13$ linoleic acid respectively.

L_2 —The same acids as mentioned in L_1 (a) were identified, e.g., dihydroxystearic acid (m.p. 129.5°) and tetrahydroxystearic acid (m.p. 170°).

S_1 —Palmitic acid (m.p. 62°) was separated.

S_2 —Stearic acid of m.p. 70° was identified.

Final data of the component acids from various ester fractions are summarised in Table IV.

TABLE IV

Acids.	Solid acids 3.33%.	Liquid acids 96.67%	Total percentage of fatty acids		Mols. ex N-S
			including N-S.	excluding Unsap. Mat.	
Caproic	—	2.74	2.1	2.2	5.2
Palmitic	1.82	—	1.8	1.9	2.0
Stearic	1.24	—	1.3	1.3	1.2
Arachidic	0.13	—	0.1	0.1	0.1
Oleic	0.14	36.32	36.5	37.6	36.3
Linoleic	—	55.07	55.1	56.9	55.2
Unsap. matter	—	3.14	3.1	—	—

Association ratio of saturated to unsaturated acids mols is 1.0 : 10.73.

Component Glycerides of Kahu Oil.—Neutral oil (100 g.) was brominated in petroleum ether solution at -5° and the brominated product was subjected to fractional separation into different fractions by absolute alcohol, acetone-alcohol and acetone. Alcohol-insoluble portion corresponded to 0.6% of trilinolein. Further work on glyceride structure is in progress. On account of very low percentage of saturated acids in the oil, no fully-saturated glycerides could be isolated.

Examination of Seeds.—Seeds were carefully heated in a crucible and the ash obtained was qualitatively analysed. It showed the presence of iron, sodium, potassium, phosphorus, aluminium, calcium, nitrates, chlorides and mere traces of arsenic.

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